

Short communication

First record of *Neoheegeria gigantea* (Thys.: Phlaeothripidae) from Iran

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چکیده

گونه‌ی *Neoheegeria gigantea* (Priesner) از خانواده‌ی Phlaeothripidae و قبیله‌ی Haplothripini برای نخستین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود. نمونه‌های این گونه در میان برگ‌های پوسیده‌ی زیر درختان بلوط جمع‌آوری شد که احتمالاً شکل تابستان‌گذران این گونه می‌باشد.

In the course of a survey on thrips associated with leaf litter, in summer 2008, in the city of Mamasani (Fars province), a total of 37 female specimens of *Neoheegeria gigantea* (Priesner) were collected from dead leaves of oak by using Berlese funnel. This is the third species of *Neoheegeria* Schmutz that is here recorded from Iran. This species is distinguished from other species of the genus in having well developed metathoracic sternopleural sutures that is completely absent in the remaining species. The relatively large population of *N. gigantea* is likely an indication of an aestivation phase of *N. gigantea* in the leaf litter of *Quercus* as most of the flowers had died in the collecting site.

To date, 45 species of the family Phlaeothripidae (Thys.: Tubulifera), mostly belonging to the subfamily Phlaeothripinae, have been recorded from Iran (Bhatti *et al.*, 2009), of which 27 species from four genera, i.e. *Dolicholepta* Priesner (with one species), *Haplothrips* Amyot & Serville (with 23 species), *Neoheegeria* (with two species), and *Plicothrips* Bhatti (with one species) are accommodated in the tribe Haplothripini (Minaei & Mound, 2008). The genus *Neoheegeria*, which is characterised by having three sensoria on antennal segment III and four sensoria on the segment IV, consists of the following four species: *N. dalmatica* Schmutz, *N. persica* Priesner, *N. sinica* Priesner and *N. gigantea* (Minaei *et al.*, 2007). The former three species are known to be mainly associated with the flowers of Lamiaceae (*Stachys* and *Phlomis*) in southern Palaearctic countries. Moreover *N. dalmatica* has been recently collected in England on *Stachys* (Collins, 2007). The species *N. gigantea*, which was described from Egypt (Priesner, 1934), is only recorded on *Cistanche lutea* (family Scrophulariaceae) (Priesner, 1965).

The majority of the specimens are deposited in the collection of Department of Plant Protection, Shiraz University.

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